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CRITICAL METALS: A RESEARCH AGENDA FOR PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Raw material criticality, whether through natural resource constraints or political maneuvering is increasingly exposing different industries that develop products to a range of adverse risk scenarios. Exploratory research was conducted to gain an insight into the awareness of companies to the challenges critical metals can present and to ascertain if action is being taken. The study clearly demonstrates a need for more research to gain a deeper insight into mitigating adverse critical metal risk throughout the different stages of the product development process. The conclusion provides an insight as to the implications for further research.

Keywords: resource depletion, sustainability, value chain

INTRODUCTION

This paper reports on the early stages of ongoing research that is focused on gaining insight into how companies can react and prepare, through product design approaches and innovation strategies, to mitigate the business and environmental risks presented by critical metals. The goal of this exploratory study is to develop a research agenda for further activities.

As a result of recent developments material availability has become an increasing challenge and is receiving increased media attention. When looking at critical metals it is important to keep the entire life-cycle of a product in mind, from the mines to processing, through design stages, manufacturing and transport, to the end-of-life of the actual product. The end-of-life can sometimes be after a second or third life, in a landfill, at incineration, possibly in a third world country or at a recycling firm.

In literature, the scarcity of metal elements currently has a variety of terms applied to it such as material scarcity, non-renewable resource scarcity, essential substances security, resource security, metal scarcity, criticality of materials, scarcity of minerals, critical raw materials, material security, critical metals, resource depletion, rare metals supply, priority materials, shortages of precious metals and commodities or a combination of the above (Peck, 2010). This paper will use the term critical metals. Other researchers have investigated metal criticality but how a company can prepare for it has received comparably less attention. The research is contradictive or non-conclusive in what way metal criticality will be a problem (for which metals, reasons for criticality, extend of the problem, etc.), and offer different time frames. Moreover, there are currently no agreed indications of metal stocks in the anthroposphere and how much of these metals can be regained (UNEP, 2010, Heida, 2010). There are many different lists on which metals are critical this paper is based on the EU list (European Commission, 2010).

Critical metals are widely used in the technologies the world relies on. They are in the computers so vital to many societies, cars that are used to commute, mobile phones, LCD screens, jet engines, lighting systems, wind turbines and solar PV panels that are needed to generate electricity, and many more applications. Critical metals have quickly become key to our way of life.

In the past century material exploitation and use has intensified in the western world. Ever since the 1980s, an increasing amount and variety of metals is used in products (Reller, 2010; Theis, 2010), mainly because of increased application of electronics, and increased product complexity (Graedel, 2007). Thus

far lack of easy accessibility of metal (elements) has never been a limiting factor for product design. Although this material prosperity has mainly been utilized by those living in the developed world, the emerging markets aspire to the same wealth and level of consumerism and have started to 'catch up'. All these developments have created an enormous demand for metals, and have caused many metal prices to continuously rise (except during recession 2008-2010). Moreover, due to fluctuating metal demands, fluctuating metal availability, and technology booms, the prices of raw materials are increasingly volatile and there is often short-term unavailability of some of the metals. Moreover the supply is very inelastic as the mining and recycling industries have very long cycle times. Besides that, the mineral resources are distributed unevenly throughout the globe, and some countries have greater reserves and mining capacities than others. This is a big risk, because some countries have already decided to first serve national demand before serving the rest of the world (China). Additionally it also being used for political pressure purposes.

In terms of producing and developing products not all companies do things in the same way, different approaches are taken with design, outsourcing, manufacturing and end of life. The strategies of companies and best practice in terms of dealing with metal criticality risk is yet unknown. The threats to a company can be significant as the lack of a material can mean that a product cannot be produced at all due to the unavailability of a critical part or a long certification period of a substitute product and its materials. This can lead to enormous losses for a company or even an entire sector. The best way to react to this threat will depend on the sector and product. Criticality of materials can be a big problem if there are no substitute materials available or for those products where certification is more difficult, for example in the aerospace industry.

This research does not investigate which metals are / will be critical, but how companies should prepare for metal shortages and what role product design can play. Nevertheless, an overview of the phenomenon and a clear definition will be given first as there is

no clear common understanding of what critical metals are and what criticality of materials means, both in literature as well as within industry.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Metal reserves / resources

As metal elements are non-renewable resources, there is a finite amount of supply in the ground. Since not all reserves have been discovered, it is difficult to predict how much of a certain metal is still available for mining. However, estimations have been made. Although there are researchers who consider the resource base to be fixed, this paper is based on a dynamic situation. The size of the reserves and resources is different for every metal element and is not fixed but dynamic, as it changes with every new discovered reserve but also if a more efficient mining technology is developed, which can make it economic to mine at lower ore grades or at remote locations. This in turn is linked to price. Mining is a very cost, resource and energy intensive activity and creates a lot of waste (Rizzolio, 2006). Building up new mining capabilities requires significant capital investments. To extract the ore from the ground, and the pure metal from ore, several complex steps have to be taken. A lot of the easier to mine - better grade ores have already been mined and refined, hence the production will have to move towards lower ore grades and in more remote locations (Angerer, 2009, Bol and Wouters, 2009). Apart from the technical difficulty, high costs, high energy demands and lower ore grades, when mining and refining at remote locations (Diederer, 2009a, Bardi, 2008), there are several challenges, as seen in the 2010 oil leak in the gulf of Mexico. Metals are rarely found in their pure form in nature and always occur in combination with other metal and non-metal materials. The metals are not in mixtures of equal quantities (co-products) but often contain a larger quantity of one carrier metal and small quantities of other metals mixed in between (by-products). That is why it can be differentiated between the major carrier metal and its co- and by-products. Therefore, the production quantities, which can be mined, of co- and by-products, are dependent on the production of the major carrier metals. Besides that, they are rarely used in their

pure form but are alloyed with other metals and materials or added as doping agents, so not every material that contains critical metals is a metal.

Material price development

The price of raw materials to produce a product has continued rising the past years (not taking the economical crisis into consideration). Figure 1 shows how the rising materials cost are taking over an increasing share of the production cost in Germany.

Figure 1: Development of costs in the manufacturing industry of Germany in constant prices (Angerer, 2009)

What are critical metals?

Critical metals are metals of which demand exceeds the ability of markets to supply. This can happen due to a number of reasons and can lead to short or long-term supply interruptions (Kooroshy, 2010). The problem of critical metals is not the availability of the material, but the accessibility, because there are many more factors than just the geological availability that can constrain resource supply. Some of the most important reasons for a metal to become critical are geopolitics, technology boosts, lack of recycling and dissipative applications, and the difference in global capital throughout the nations. It is therefore a complex and global challenge. The causes of criticality are divided into demand and supply related causes. Demand related causes being those that lead to an increase in demand of a certain material and supply related causes those that lead to a decrease in resource accessibility (Wolfensberger-Malo, 2007). Table 2 provides an overview of the causes for criticality. In most cases no single reason will cause relative criticality by itself, but the interplay of factors can cause supply disruptions. One of the hardest things about critical metals is predicting how long the supply interruptions will last. Sometimes it is only a few days, weeks or

months and in other cases it can take years. In the latter, simply mitigating the risk will not be proficient as the supply shortages are permanent for the time being. Furthermore critical metals do not suffer from supply interruptions all at the same time, but depending on the underlying reasons, at different moments in time. Moreover, when analyzing the causes for criticality it is important to keep in mind both the primary as well as the secondary production of metal commodities, as both have an influence on the criticality of a metal. If, for example, the anthropogenic metal stock is completely depleted, it can still be recycled - albeit with cyclical reduction in grade. The metal therefore may not be critical, even though it is depleted.

Critical metals and the EU

The European Union (EU) has limited strategic critical metal resources, along with a few national stockpiles, and can therefore not ensure material supplies to European companies. It is therefore highly dependent on both imports and recycling. Mining and production of metals has been moved to locations that are economically more attractive, and that have lighter regulatory standards. The mining activities in the European Union and the United States have therefore declined (Mudd, 2007, Ericsson, 2010).

The EU has made a list of critical raw materials based on their high relative supply risk and their high relative economic importance. It was published in June 2010 and takes into account the substitutability between materials and first and secondary raw materials. It identified 14 major critical metals, amongst which rare earth metals¹, platinum group metals² and Indium (European Commission, 2010). Additionally, the European Union's 2020 Energy Vision has labeled critical metals as one of the major issues that have to be tackled to be able to ensure a sustainable energy supply.

¹ Rare Earths is a group of 17 chemical elements: scandium (Sc), yttrium (Y) and the 15 lanthanides (La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Pm, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, Lu).

² The platinum group metals consist of ruthenium (Ru), rhodium (Rh), palladium (Pd), osmium (Os), iridium (Ir) and platinum (Pt).

Timescale	Supply-related causes	Demand related causes
Permanent	1. Geological <i>Mineral depletion</i>	1. Functional <i>Basic needs</i>
	2. Technological <i>Dissipation</i>	
Temporary	<i>Feasibility of substitution</i> <i>Inefficient / no recycling</i> <i>Interruption of trade</i> <i>Entrance barriers</i>	2. Demographic <i>Population growth</i>
	3. Societal <i>Regulatory</i> <i>Geopolitical</i> <i>Social</i>	3. Social <i>Culture</i> <i>Wealth / poverty</i> <i>Lifestyle</i>
	4. Economic <i>High volatility of sectors</i> <i>Insufficient investments</i> <i>Interruption of trade</i> <i>Entrance barriers</i>	

Table 1: Overview reasons for criticality of materials (Wolfensberger-Malo, 2007)

Critical metals and product development

Throughout the past decennia material usage has not been a limiting factor in product development, as the diversity of materials that are available on the market continues to increase (Bol, 2009). The only limitation for design so far has been the material price. Furthermore, the long list of metal composites, last minute changes to a product, and incomplete material bills, make it very difficult to keep an overview of the different metals that went into a product.

Nonetheless, critical metals will over time become an increasing risk for the different product developing industries (Graedel, 2007). Currently, China, the producer of up to 97% of the rare earth metals in the world, has been limiting its critical metal export (Strategic-Metal-Investments, 2010). Therefore the world has reached the point where it appears that demand has outgrown the supply for some metals (Reller, 2010).

Critical metals are used in many of the products essential to the modern way of life. Ranging from semiconductors, computers, mobile phones, LCD screens, cars, jet engines, high-tech equipment, LED lighting and high performance alloys, to sustainable technologies that are essential for the green energy industry, like batteries for hybrid cars, photovoltaic's and wind turbines. Without critical metals all these products could at the moment not be produced to their current designs (Angerer, 2009, Morley and Eatherley, 2008, Rademaker and

Kooroshy, 2010, Marin, 2006). This restriction is likely to constrain future developments. To ensure that we can keep on relying on these technologies, it is important to substitute the critical metals where possible and increase recycling within the Europe (Reller, 2010).

Metal recycling

One of the biggest challenges is the lack of a proper closed-loop system, and that many of the valuable metals end up in landfills, or are sent to developing countries for recycling. There the recycling is often carried out in a hazardous, basic way to retrieve major metals and therefore a lot of the precious critical metals are lost. Moreover the countries are giving away their valuable metal alloys to other countries, like for example China, for free, instead of properly recycling the products themselves, to maintain ownership and access. The technologies to fully recycle products and regain the valuable metals are available, the developed economies just have to invest, develop and use them (Buchert, 2009).

Coping strategies

Simply mining more minerals once demand goes up is not possible. It is often not possible to simply mine more, as building up new mining capacities takes five to twelve years and requires an investment in the billions (Ecclestone, 2010). Additionally, most critical metals are mined as by-products. Increasing the mining of one metal means increasing the mining

of the major-metal and of the other by-products, which can cause an over-production of the other metals, and can create volatile metal markets. In the EU Commission’s Raw Materials Initiative by HCSS three policy recommendations were named in the category ‘Resource efficiency & reduction of EU primary raw material consumption’ that are of relevance for this project: (1) foster substitution, (2) promote recycling and (3) facilitate the use of secondary raw materials (Rademaker and Kooroshy, 2010). The research by Maya Wolfensberger-Malo (2007) showed, that the five experts that were asked considered (1) efficient materials use, (2) high environmental standards for new technologies, (3) the continued search for new technologies based on abundant elements, (4) the adjustment of technology expectations to long-term constraints and (5) the repeated monitoring of the process of choice and its long-term consequences, the most promising strategies proposed by Andersson in 2001. Table 2 shows an overview of several strategies and how they could be implemented. Most of these strategies are very general and can be executed in many different ways.

Coping strategy	Measure
Find new deposits	By fostering public funding in researching sub-economic deposits
Retard growth in consumption	By changing consumer preferences and behavior
	By altering purchase decision and the intensity of use
	By altering urban form changes
	By material substitution
Increase efficiency	By minimizing lifecycle costs
	By prolongating the products lifespan
	By nanotechnology
Encourage recycling	By design for disassembly
	By conditioning the consumers to return products
	By conditioning the sellers to take products back
	By legislation
Avoid dissipation	By legislation
	By forecasting technological progress

Table 2: Coping strategies (in bold) and its required measures (Wolfensberger-Malo, 2007)

A lot of the measures can be directly or indirectly executed or influenced by product development and innovation (Ritter, 2009), but require close collaboration with the different parts of the supply chain.

So far a companies role in dealing with critical metals, has received little attention and is not fully addressed in literature. Focusing mainly on material research, without addressing product development, supply chain management, and business model innovation, and without involving companies, can be seen to be a missed opportunity. This informed our next steps of the research.

METHODOLOGY

Exploratory research was conducted to gain a better understanding of the phenomena and to gain more insight into the awareness of the problem within industry and the role product development can play in dealing with critical metals. A series of eleven interviews was conducted, within different high-tech companies, to assess the awareness of critical metal risk. The interviews were carried out at an automotive, industrial machinery, consumer electronics and two healthcare equipment companies. The companies chosen demonstrate a wide variance in the characteristics and capabilities to be investigated. They differ on aspects such as the product complexity, product requirements, product lifetime, product portfolio size, the target market and the division of responsibility between research, supply chain management and product development. All companies offer high quality and high-end goods, with some exceptions that serve a range of consumer groups with low- to high-end products. The different companies have a different product portfolio size and diversity. Some product portfolio’s being very big with a high diversity whereas others are relatively small specialized in one product category. Most of the companies that participated are active in the b2b market with two exceptions, one company that focuses on the b2c market and one company that caters both markets. All companies use critical metals in some way or another. Table 3 provides an overview of the different cases.

Company	Type of products	Amount of interviews
Company 1 (pilot case)	(mainly small) high-tech and low-tech products	1
Company 2	High-tech medical equipment	3
Company 3	High-tech laboratory equipment	1
Company 4	Automotive	1
Company 5	High-tech consumer goods	3
Company 6	High-tech laboratory equipment	1

Table 3: Overview cases

The goal of the interviews was to gain a holistic overview of the opinions on critical metal issues of the parties involved in product development. During the interviews it was probed whether the respondents are aware of material criticality, how the company develops products, whether they take active measures during product development and supply chain management regarding critical metals and whether they have / have not adjusted their strategies and activities to lower the critical metal risk and the reasoning behind it. Respondents were from the following functions; material research, product design, corporate social responsibility (CSR) / sustainability, component sourcing, product lifecycle management and supply chain management.

The interviews were semi-structured in-depth interviews and a checklist was used to ensure all topics would be covered (Yin, 2009). The checklist consists of a general part that focuses on the innovation and product development process of the company and the division of responsibilities during this process. The second part focuses on the critical metal risk:

- Whether the company has had problems with material or component supply in the past
- Where they think that they are most at risk, their weaknesses
- Who is responsible for dealing with critical metals
- Whether they are currently taking any action to reduce it and in what way

- At which point during the product development process and lifetime the product can be altered
- Whether they see any opportunities related to material criticality

PILOT INTERVIEW

To test the checklist a pilot interview was conducted. For the pilot interview a high-tech company with a low product portfolio diversity (one general specialization) that serves both the b2b as well as the b2c market was chosen. For the data gathering one interview, one corporate presentation about the company, its organization and its qualifications as well as online data was used. Based on the outcome the topic guide for the interviews was adjusted.

DATA ANALYSIS

Most interviews were recorded, saved and analyzed. During those interviews that were not recorded notes were taken to ensure that no insights are lost or left neglected. The data analysis was first conducted within-case (company) and then cross-case.

RESULTS

CRITICAL METAL USAGE

Awareness of critical metal risks

The internal awareness of the overall phenomenon is low and fragmented. The different supply- and demand-related reasons for a metal to be critical are not known throughout the organizations, and not every one of them is considered a threat. Even so, in none of the companies that participated metal criticality was seen as a topic of strategic interest and therefore incorporated into company strategies. Most companies considered the supply of critical metals an issue that will become important in the future and demand related supply issues worried them most.

Internal responsibility for dealing with critical metal issues

Within the different companies people at different levels and in different parts of the organization were responsible for / or thinking about dealing with critical metals. In two companies it was dealt with at

the top level and within supply chain management, without communicating the issues throughout the company. In two other companies the people that were feeling responsible were at the head of the engineering department. This happened without their top management knowing about it. In one company it was the material laboratory that had “unofficially” taken on the responsibility without the top management knowing.

External responsibility for dealing with critical metal issues

In all companies suppliers (first-tier) were considered responsible for the things (materials, part, sub-assemblies, assemblies & products) they deliver and had to make sure critical metal issues would not impact their capability to deliver on time. In practice however their first tier suppliers are not always prepared and able to compensate for increased lead times. When a small business supplies parts to them, they can also not hold them responsible for losses due to increased lead time, nor could they expect them to be aware of critical metal issues and do preventive market analysis.

CRITICAL METALS AND THE ENTIRE PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

Intervention point(s) to deal with critical metals

All companies that develop platform-based products agreed that in case a critical metal could not be supplied, not every part of a product can simply be altered at any time.

In case an add-on part is vulnerable it can be more easily adjusted. In that case the only restrictions to replacement are the available space and the connection point to the rest of the product. If however a part of the platform itself needs to be redeveloped it would be a bigger problem because the functionality, properties and technology are designed in accordance with the parts around it and the whole system. Simply substituting one material by another one, while maintaining the same characteristics, is therefore often not possible. Changing a critical part of a platform therefore often means redesigning the whole platform. One of the companies that participated is considering whether they should try to avoid and / or minimize the use of

critical metals in the platform they will start to develop in the near future.

Many respondents mentioned that if they tried to avoid critical metals in their design it would probably increase the development times, increase research & development efforts, increase testing times and efforts and increase the cost of a new platform. Moreover, it would be hard to predict the extra resources needed to develop a product/platform with the same quality level without the use of critical metals. Therefore these kinds of alterations and platform changes can only be done with management support to get access to the resources that would be needed.

The product life-cycle

One company developed products that had an average official lifetime of about 10 years. During these ten years regular service and sometimes refurbishment was necessary to keep the product functioning. At the end of its lifetime the product was often sold to Eastern Europe for a second life and eventually from there to developing countries for a third and final life. Another company offered a take-back and trade-in system when buying a new model. The old products are then refurbished and sold again for a fraction of the original price. A third company mentioned that they currently did not have any systems to offer second and third lives, but that they were considering collecting their products or parts of their products again at the end of life to retrieve the materials.

End-of-life

None of the products are developed in such a way that they can be easily disassembled at the end of life. While some products need regular maintenance and can therefore be taken completely apart, others are made for easy assembly only and therefore not to be taken apart at any point in their life-cycle. One of the companies had recently developed a flagship eco version of one of its products to investigate issues like design for disassembly, avoidance of toxic materials and recycling.

Bill of materials (BOM)

None of the companies knew their entire BOM including all the detailed specifications of the

electronics. Without the electronics, some companies were rather confident that they knew nearly the entire BOM, because they develop most of their products and parts in house. All companies highlighted that it was a big problem that they did not know the entire BOM and that without it they are unable to predict the risk they have due to critical metals.

SUPPLY CHAIN

Manufacturing & geopolitics

All the companies outsource large parts of their manufacturing, some within Europe and others in Asia and more specifically in China. Because China is the major supplier of many critical metals, the developments in China's politics (announcing restricted export, access to IPR and the recent restriction on alloy exports) are making the companies increasingly nervous. Half of the companies are closely watching China because they do not possess manufacturing there, and fear losing access to the raw materials and parts that they need. Besides that, several companies said that the WTO and the EU should step up to China and defend their interests.

Value chain involvement

All respondent mentioned that they were involved or were thinking about getting involved with their second and in some cases even third tier suppliers (for crucial parts only). Even companies that had previously worked towards obtaining a leaner supply chain are revisiting that decision and have decided to get more and more involved. Until now they had outsourced a lot of activities including the selection of suppliers (second tier) by their own suppliers (first tier). Some of the companies also keep a set of alternative suppliers for parts / sub-assemblies / assemblies, to ensure that, in case of supply interruptions, the company could retrieve its supplies from elsewhere.

Besides that, in some of the companies crucial parts of products are supplied by multiple suppliers on a daily basis, even if it costs more.

Another company has decided to increase the buffer stocks of a certain material that is essential to their products. Of course substituting it with a different

material is preferable but they stated that it would require a large investment to find the right combination of formula and production techniques to get the unique properties they need.

Supplier collaboration

All companies said that to get more transparency into what every product is made of it is important to get involved with and collaborate with their suppliers. The new REACH regulation that is expected to contain 105 materials (compared to the less than 20 thus far) has already stimulated the development and use of tools like BOM-check, IMDS, etc.. Eventually this will lead to more transparency but when initiating the data collection companies mentioned that it was a lot of work to get suppliers to participate. Apart from that, suppliers also feel that their competitive advantage is harmed by sharing the composition of their material alloys and the quantities of the different critical metals that are in them.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

DEALING WITH METAL CRITICALITY

Although several of the respondents said they have problems with the supply of critical metals or components derived from them, only very few have started taking action. Furthermore respondents indicated that they were not sure how to properly deal with critical metals within the product development process and the knowledge gap there is on the topic within the company. When selecting the materials, during new platform or product development, the metals that will become critical throughout the products production lifetime have to be kept in mind. Depending on the type of product this can be up to ten years and sometimes even longer. When making predictions, about which materials will become critical, it is important to consider not only current applications, but also future technology and market developments. This also holds for selecting substitute materials and technologies, as it is important to select substitutes that provide a long-term solution and not dependant on materials that will become critical in due course. A factor to keep in mind during material and technology selection is the maintenance throughout

the product life-cycle. Many products require spare parts that have to be available throughout the entire lifetime of the project, which can be up to 20, 30 or even more years depending on the product.

DIVISION OF RESPONSIBILITIES

The interviews in industry have shown that critical metals are embedded in parts purchased by the original equipment manufacturer (OEM) without awareness of the criticality of the metals therein, sometimes even not to the knowledge of the supplying company itself. Moreover it is not an issue that is recognized companywide in all departments, but often only in a small part of the company. The overall awareness is relatively low and mainly present within the department that is responsible for or is dealing with critical metals (officially or unofficially). In none of the companies the problem with all its facets was communicated clearly towards all employees as a topic of strategic interest. There are numerous things that can be done to reduce the risk both during product design as well as in the supply chain. It is therefore important to look at the entire product development system from a holistic point of view, starting at the Fuzzy front End (FFE) of innovation, all the way through the supply chain and manufacturing, to the user and eventually the end-of-life. Addressing critical metals is therefore not just a supply chain, or product development problem but should be addressed at all levels, and through better collaboration between the departments in a company. Although the overall product development cycle is comparable, being longer or shorter depending on the kind of product a company produces, some of the companies have increased the involvement of supply chain management at the early stages of the new product development (NPD) process. This is done to ensure better collaboration, and decision-making in terms of technology, parts and material selection, and to avoid problems later on in the supply chain, by preventing them at the stage (FFE) where the crucial decisions are made. However most OEM's consider their suppliers responsible for delivering a part, or component that contains critical metals. They also expect them to take action to reduce the risk, and / or to investigate substituting the metal or technology.

VALUE CHAIN COLLABORATION

There is a lack of cross-organizational awareness and collaboration, which makes it harder for companies to assess the size of the problem, address the issue and implement changes, not only within the company, but also within the value chain.

Additionally, companies have currently positioned themselves in a reactive position, when it comes to dealing with critical metals. They are not informing suppliers (and vice versa) and are hardly engaging in value chain collaboration to tackle the problem.

Moreover, having problems with material supply is something companies do not like to admit and it is often seen as a competitive disadvantage.

Besides that it is such a complex problem that it is not always identified as one phenomenon and although some of the causes are on the radar others are not. This lack of cross-organizational awareness makes it harder to assess the size of the problem, address the issue and implement changes. Overall, it can be said that the companies were hardly aware of critical metals but are starting to notice more and more supply interruptions.

RECYCLING AND PRODUCT LIFE EXTENSION

Using recycled materials in a product is done only in very few of the products that were investigated and reusing parts and / or components in new products is hardly carried out at all. Therefore this is an area where huge gains can be made, if companies can find a way to make it work. For example, a mobile phone is replaced, in Europe, on average every 0,5 to 1 years, although it was designed to last for several years and uses many components that could last a lot longer. Reusing parts and components, as well as using recycled materials, requires a mind shift, because a new product should not have to contain only virgin parts and materials. Of course this kind of reuse has to be regulated and procedures have to be installed to ensure safety and quality standards are met. Furthermore it should be aimed at developing closed-loop cycles and improved product recycling / reuse to ensure a constant level of material supply. To be able to do this recycling techniques have to be improved to be able to extract and regain all materials that contain critical metals.

STRATEGIES FOR DEALING WITH CRITICAL METALS

Improvements can be made in all areas of the product life-cycle, however making changes comes at a price. Investments have to be made in research, product redevelopment, safety stocks, diversified suppliers and possibly even system and business model changes. Because most of the companies that were investigated have only just started to consider the topic and have not taken action yet, it is too soon to say which strategies work best. Some companies have chosen to deal with it by altering their supply chain. Another approach seriously considered is taking critical metals into account at the beginning of product and platform development. A third approach is to develop a (company specific) 'red list' of materials that can be used during material selection to ensure that certain metals will not be used, unless it really cannot be avoided. A fourth way of dealing with it is by involving purchasing (for advice) at the early stages of the FFE to make the right technology- and product-choices at an early stage to prevent the use of certain metals, components and parts later on in the process. A fifth way of dealing with critical metals is by using an increasing amount of recycled materials rather than virgin stock and a sixth approach is to increase the recycling /reuse of products to regain the materials. This is however a solution that companies cannot establish by themselves because a national and preferably an international (EU) network for collection and recycling is needed as well as European regulations.

THERE IS OFTEN NO EASY SOLUTION

Respondents mentioned that it can be very appealing to simply increase the safety stocks when a material is prone to some degree of volatility, it only works for a limited amount of time and a limited amount of metals at once. This solution includes high-investments and fixed capital, and does not offer a long term solution if the supply interruption continues over a longer period of time. Each material has different attributes (corrosion, electrical conductivity, density, flexibility, strength, flow, ...) which leads to other design & engineering criteria and production methods. Substituting one material with another is therefore not as easy as it sounds. In many cases, especially when a part has a

critical function, one cannot just change the material for production, because different alloys have different properties and the parts will have to be altered to fit the criteria of the substitute material. Changing the metal means redesigning the part and possibly the product as well as changing the manufacturing process.

In many of the complex platform-based products that were investigated, critical metals can only be eliminated if they are part of the add-ons. If they are however part of the core platform chances are big that the whole platform has to be redeveloped, which takes between two to ten years, depending on the product. Moreover in case the metal that has to be substituted is essential to the core technology, it can be that substituting the metal means switching technologies.

AWARENESS OF DESIGNERS / DESIGN ENGINEERS

Product designers are often unaware of the materials that are needed to manufacture the prefabricated assemblies they use (Koehler, 2009). They select them based on appearance and specifications unaware of the 'black boxes' they are. Whether or not this material will be easily accessible is never considered. These decisions however can have a tremendous impact on material usage and thus on the product risk.

CONCLUSIONS AND RESEARCH AGENDA

Critical metals are and will increasingly present a challenge, especially for the high-tech, energy and automotive industry. They are essential to the modern way of life and the window of opportunity to make a smooth, timely transition is closing. Companies and governments have to start acting now, to ensure that they will be able to deal with future product and energy demands. Moreover with peak oil it is important to find a solution for the energy problem soon, because both green and conventional energy technologies require a lot of critical metals.

When it comes to preparing for, and dealing with possible metal criticality issues, product innovation and Supply chain management (strategic sourcing) go hand in hand. The knowledge to tackle these issues is spread over the different elements of the product development process and can only be effectively

dealt with through innovation, cross-functional teamwork and good knowledge management. To be able to innovate and make changes, a company must know which metals are most likely to be critical, and where they are currently being used and in which future products and technologies they will be applied. As many companies outsource parts of their (strategic) sourcing, engineering and production activities the supplier network can be enormous and knowing what exact material is put into each single part can be a challenge (for example computer chips).

No matter how small / big or diverse the product portfolio is one uncertain element hits all high-tech products: the electronics. It is a risk factor in all products because it is currently not transparent what metals are used in what electronic components and nobody really has data on all the sub-components of every miniature electronic element that is part of their system. Since one small processor can consist of several hundred parts many of which are made with critical metals.

We are currently using more metals elements than ever and they are essential to all the products and technologies we need and to those we love to use. Although the European Union has established a first list of critical raw materials in June 2010, industry and material research have not yet caught up. Only a fraction of the materials scientists that are out there are aware of the criticality of some of the metal elements and are doing research on substitute materials.

Several companies mentioned critical metals could be an incentive for developing better recycling facilities and recycling initiatives in Europe as a lot of the critical metals could be regained in that way. However how exactly such a recycling effort could look like fell outside the scope of this project but is definitely worth further investigation.

Because of the REACH regulation there are now some digital tools available to manage the bill of materials throughout the value chain. These tools however are made to ensure compliance and not to identify parts or components that contain critical metals.

Moreover, metal prices are increasingly volatile and will probably be the first incentive for companies to act. Nevertheless, reducing the critical metals risk will require a lot of investment in research,

technology and product (re)development up-front to prevent problems in the future.

It can be concluded that design decisions taken at the various stages of the NPD process need to take the criticality of certain metals into account. This is not just done by composing a 'Design for Criticality' strategy, but most likely requires a fundamentally different design approach, and calls for a collaborative setting of co-designing with partners and suppliers. Furthermore the span of (unconscious) influence of upstream suppliers needs to be taken into account already at the early stages of the NPD process to successfully mitigate the risk.

When it comes to dealing with critical metals, no matter what strategy a company will choose to implement conscious material usage into their day-to-day activities, there will often be a lack of the required knowledge, experience, design skills, leadership and integration of the value chain to deal with the challenge. To be able to make this transition, and keep on innovating in the meanwhile, a company might have to find ways to gain and spread knowledge throughout their entire value chain, from the product development teams (including fuzzy front end) to activities and services that are outsourced, for example manufacturing. As material/metal conscious product development is not a widely spread phenomenon, there is no best practice of how to implement material awareness into a company strategy, its products and its supply chain.

Overall it can be said that this is a problem that can be tackled, however it does require smart thinking, the willingness to change, good collaboration within and between firms in the value chain, and planning ahead.

TOWARDS A RESEARCH AGENDA

This research was of exploratory nature to gain as many insights as possible and therefore does not provide empirical evidence.

The results informed our next step of research that aims to deepen our understanding of the consequences of critical metals on the design process. As many of the companies that were investigated divided the responsibility for dealing with critical metals in a very different way, a next step would be to investigate more companies to look

at the division of responsibilities and to find out why one company chooses to deal with it within engineering and another on supply chain level. Currently none of the companies that were investigated had truly taken action to reduce the risk and most of them were still considering their options and being inconclusive about what would work best. Therefore, it would be interesting to follow companies over time to see what approach they choose for reducing critical metal risk and the process they go through.

PROPOSED RESEARCH AGENDA:

- What is the best practice for mitigating critical metal risk
- What changes have to be made within a company and its value chain to successfully deal with critical metals
- How can value chain collaboration be applied to gain a better insight in critical metal usage and to reduce the risk
- What division of responsibilities leads to the best results when dealing with critical metals
- What are the knowledge gaps within companies and their value chain when it comes to mitigating critical metal risk
- What methods can companies apply to strategically select materials and technologies in the early stages of product development
- What role can designers play in dealing with critical metals

Because there is little research conducted on how companies can deal with critical metals, there is a lot of opportunity and a need to do more research. Both investigating the improvements that can be made to the supply chain and the handling of critical metals throughout the value chain, as well as how product design and innovation can help, are topics in need of more research.

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